

Examining the Link Between Diabetes Prevalence and Health Literacy in Brazil

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Topic: Diabetes and health literacy

Title: Examining the Link Between Diabetes Prevalence and Health Literacy in Brazil

Objectives: To evaluate current literature on the relationship between health literacy in Brazil and prevalence of diabetes, a non-communicable disease (NCD), to support the development of effective public health strategies designed for people living in the country.

Background: The 2019 Brazilian National Health Survey reported a crude prevalence of diabetes of 7.7%, a 24% increase from 2013. Diabetes has long been a public health concern in Brazil as differences in education can limit the effectiveness of public health efforts, especially with underserved populations. While healthcare professionals have investigated the prevalence of diabetes and health literacy independently, their relationship has yet to be extensively studied. Therefore, understanding the relationship between health literacy rate and prevalence of diabetes is crucial to develop more targeted and effective education programs for the Brazilian healthcare system.

Methods: I conducted a bibliometric search using the Web of Science core collection database with the keywords: “Brazil,” “diabetes prevalence,” and “health education.” This generated 239 preliminary results and I exported the data into Google Sheets. Then, I excluded studies that focused on diabetes intervention and selected 100 most cited articles relevant to the topic for analysis.

Results: Amongst the 100 most cited articles, the common author keywords include “diabetes mellitus,” “metabolic syndrome,” “prevalence,” “brazil,” and “health education.” Overall, only 14 articles mentioned both diabetes and health literacy or education in Brazil. The remaining 86 articles primarily focused on diabetes trends and their associations with risk factors such as gender, age, and income amongst Brazilian populations.

Conclusions: Institutions should prioritize examining trends in diabetes and Brazilians’ health literacy to address the knowledge gap in understanding how the factors can influence each other. This can help public health institutions to make effective interventions in lowering diabetes occurrence in the country.

Keyword 1: Brazil

Keyword 2: Diabetes prevalence

Keyword 3: Health education

Keyword 4: Health literacy

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